

WROCLAW UNIVERSITY
OF ENVIRONMENTAL
AND LIFE SCIENCES

FACULTY OF ENVIRONMENTAL
ENGINEERING AND GEODESY
WROCLAW UNIVERSITY OF ENVIRONMENTAL
AND LIFE SCIENCES

Syllabus for the 1st GATHERS Summer School

1 School overview

The school comprises theoretical and practical classes in:

- Interferometric Synthetic Aperture Radar (InSAR)
- Light Detection and Ranging (LiDAR)
- Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS) seismology

for monitoring and modelling the Earth's surface deformations and seismic risk. The school also includes a workshop on InSAR, LiDAR, GNSS and GNSS-seismology for monitoring of surface deformations and remote sensing for land cover/land use change mapping, a soft skills training, and group work in a seminar for solving and presenting of particular scientific tasks in the three above-mentioned domains.

2 Units organising the Summer School

The 1st GATHERS Summer School is organised by the Institute of Geodesy and Geoinformatics (IGiG) a unit at the Faculty of Environmental, part of the structure of the Wrocław University of Environmental Life and Sciences (UPWr) in Poland. The school is organised together with the Delft University of Technology (TU Delft, the Netherlands), Technische Universität Wien (TU Wien, Austria), and Sapienza University of Rome (Italy) within the frames of the Horizon 2020 Twinning Project "GATHERS – Integration of Geodetic and imAging TecHniques for monitoring and modelling the Earth's surface defoRmations and Seismic risk".

3 Target group

The school program is built for MSc and PhD students, as well as young specialist and researchers with a background in geodesy, remote sensing, computer science, environmental engineering, geography, geodynamics, geophysics, or related fields.

4 Recruitment procedure

The candidates for the school submit motivation letters which are evaluated by a committee of three members of the GATHERS consortium. The criteria for selection includes field of study and scientific

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interests, level of study, former experience in the GATHERS topics, former experience in geosciences, geodesy, remote sensing, etc.

5 Courses description

5.1 Interferometric Synthetic Aperture Radar (InSAR)

5.1.1 InSAR theory

Sessions/workload: 3 hours (19.09.2022, 11:00-12:30 & 14:00-15:30)

Teaching delivery methods: Face-to-face interactive lecture, also with usage of a multimedia

Content overview: An introduction in the principles of satellite-based Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) systems, the SAR satellite orbit and imaging geometry, radar signal characteristics, SAR observations. Overview of the Interferometric SAR (InSAR) technique, interferometric coherence and InSAR observations, technique limitations and sources of errors. A review of the different processing approaches – Differential InSAR, subsequent interferograms, Small Baseline Subset (SBAS), Persistent Scatterer Interferometry (PSI), as well as phase unwrapping procedure. Discussion on interpretation of InSAR data – resolution, surface deformation, orbits in the light of decomposition and sensitivity, validation and integration of the InSAR results, and comparison with other geodetic techniques.

Learning objectives - by the end of this course students will be able to:

- understand the SAR, InSAR and PSI principles, interferometric phase and coherence characteristics and usage
- learn the advantages and limitations in surface deformation detection by InSAR, know the sources of errors;
- identify the InSAR main application areas and decide on the proper processing approach.

Lecturers:

Freek van Leijen, PhD, MSc, is senior researcher and teacher at Delft University of Technology and development manager InSAR at SkyGeo. He has over 20 years of experience in satellite radar interferometry and deformation analysis. Freek obtained his master degree in Geodetic Engineering at Delft University of Technology in 2002. In 2003, he re-joined Delft University of Technology as a PhD-student, working on satellite radar interferometric research. He develops software algorithms for Persistent Scatterer interferometry.

Ramon Hanssen, Prof., PhD, MSc, is Antoni van Leeuwenhoek professor in Geodesy and Earth Observation at Delft University of Technology. His work centres around fundamental and applied problems in geodesy and satellite earth observation. In particular, he pioneered the geodetic use of synthetic aperture radar interferometry, as a high-precision technique to measure deformations of the earth's surface. He is author of two patents, and his monograph on radar interferometry is the highest cited book in the domain, with nearly 2300 citations in 2018.

5.1.2 InSAR tutorials

Sessions/workload: 3.5 hours (19.09.2022, 16:00-18:00 & 20.09.2022, 09:00-10:30)

Teaching delivery methods: Practical interactive learning, also by the usage of a multimedia, work on an internet-based platform

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Content overview: Interactive exploration and analysis of PSI results over the underground mining area in Silesia, Poland. Individual assessment of the results, with peer-consultation, based on the InSAR theory session. Interactive discussion on the results, the detected surface deformations, source of errors.

Learning objectives: By the end of this course students will be able to interpret the InSAR, and in particular PSI, results in the light of geodynamic processes related with underground mining activities and analyse displacement field at the basic level.

Lecturers: Freek van Leijen, Ramon Hanssen and

Maya Ilieva, Phd, MSc, obtained her PhD degree in Geosciences in 2011 from University "Pierre and Marrie Curie"-Paris VI, France. From 2011 till 2017 she worked in University of Architecture, Civil Engineering and Geodesy (UACEG), Sofia, Bulgaria. She was a guest lecturer in remote sensing to University of Mining and geology, Sofia (2015-2020). Since 2017 she works in IGiG-UPWr where she is involved in InSAR investigations on mining induced subsidence in the area of Silesia, Poland.

5.2 Light Detection and Ranging (LiDAR)

5.2.1 LiDAR theory

Sessions/workload: 3 hours (20.09.2022, 11:00-12:30 & 14:00-15:30)

Teaching delivery methods: Face-to-face interactive lecture, also with usage of a multimedia

Content overview: An introduction in LiDAR principle – geometry and physics; interpretation of point density and multiple echoes; review of scanning mechanisms and familiarization with Airborne LiDAR (data acquisition and sensors); direct georeferencing; overview of sources of errors and strip adjustment; surface interpolation; discussion on the generation of Digital Surface Model (DSM), point cloud filtering/classification, Digital Terrain Model (DTM), DEM of Difference (DOD).

Learning objectives - by the end of this course students will be able to:

- summarize the basic operational characteristics of LiDAR instruments and platforms used for topographic mapping and geospatial applications;
- describe the basic principles of airborne LiDAR data acquisition, georeferencing, and processing of LiDAR data for topographic purposes, i.e. creating of DSM and DTM;
- apply acquired knowledge and critical thinking skills to solve a real-world problem with appropriate LiDAR data processing and analysis methods.

Lecturer: **Norbert Pfeifer**, Prof, PhD, MSc, is the head of the photogrammetry research group within the Department of Geodesy and Geoinformation, TU Wien. He worked at TU Delft, Section of Photogrammetry and Remote Sensing (Netherlands), as assistant professor and at the University of Innsbruck, Department of Geography (Austria), as lecturer. His expertise lies in geometric modelling and calibration of LiDAR and photographic image data, application in environmental sciences and he currently coordinates ~10 projects.

5.2.2 LiDAR tutorials

Sessions/workload: 3.5 hours (20.09.2022, 16:00-18:00 & 21.09.2022, 09:00-10:30)

Teaching delivery methods: Practical interactive learning, also by the usage of a multimedia, work with a specialised software

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Content overview: The students individually perform selected stages of LiDAR processing with the OPALS software. The focus is put on quality control (to check point density and geometric accuracy) and on computing DSM and DTM. Finally, the presented tools are used to investigate the deformations that occurred between 2011 and 2021 in Rybnik (Poland) using official LiDAR data.

Learning objectives: By the end of these tutorials the students will be familiar with the most important aspects of LiDAR data (quality control and derivation of surface and terrain models). Furthermore, the students will be able to perform the basic steps for processing LiDAR data in the OPALS software.

Lecturer: Camillo Ressi, PhD, MSc, obtained his doctoral degree in 2003 from TU Wien and has been a Staff Scientist within the Research Group of Photogrammetry since then. His main research interests are the calibration and processing of image data (photos, Lidar), parameter estimation and orientation of various sensors. He is referee for many international journals and associate editor of the Journal of Photogrammetry, Remote Sensing and Geoinformation Science (PFG).

5.2.3 Field measurements (UAV)

Sessions/workload: 1.5 hours (23.09.2022, 14:00-15:30)

Teaching delivery methods: Practical interactive learning

Content overview: Hands-on experience of UAV-borne LiDAR measuring campaign, collection of test measurement.

Learning objectives: By the end of this course students will be aware of activities related to UAV campaigns (preparation, executive phase including some restrictions and precautions for UAV flights), also will be familiar with the UAV platform and sensors used in the most popular UAV-borne LiDAR systems.

Lecturers:

Grzegorz Jozkow, Prof, PhD, MSc, defended his PhD in Photogrammetry and Remote Sensing in 2010 at UPWr. In the years 2013-2016 he worked as post-doctoral researcher at The Ohio State University (USA). He conducted research on: airborne laser scanning data accuracy and filtering algorithms, building digital terrain models from airborne laser scanning data and its use in environmental applications; laser scanning data compression. He is involved in research related to mapping with unmanned aerial systems using cameras and laser scanners.

Wojciech Sowa, MSc, is an assistant in the Institute of Geodesy and Geoinformatics at UPWr, teaching in the field of geodetic measurements and analyses of surface deformations, photogrammetry and remote sensing, photogrammetry in engineering measurements, unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV) systems in geodesy, digital photogrammetry, spatial Information systems, and others. He is licenced UAV pilot, involved in many projects which use data obtained from drone missions.

5.3 Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS) seismology

5.3.1 GNSS-seismology theory

Sessions/workload: 3 hours (22.09.2022, 9:00-10:30 & 11:00-12:30)

Teaching delivery methods: Face-to-face interactive lecture, also with usage of a multimedia

Content overview: An introduction on the principles of GNSS systems and data processing, GNSS measurement errors and ways to eliminate their impact, atmospheric physics, ambiguities, site

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displacements, handling precise orbits. An overview of the GNSS measurement techniques: static, kinematic and RTK, overview of GNSS software packages for high precision analysis, international sources of GNSS data and products. Introduction to variometric approach, its application to GNSS-seismology, and to the VADASE method.

Learning objectives - by the end of this course students will be able to:

- demonstrate understanding of the GPS signal, measurement models and error sources;
- describe the differences between relative and autonomous GNSS positioning, Precise Point Positioning, Differential and Variometric Approaches;
- understand the practical applications of GNSS, and in particular for seismology

Lecturers:

Mattia Crespi, Prof, PhD, MSc, received PhD in Geodesy and Surveying in 1992 at Politecnico di Torino (Turin, Italy). He is a Professor of Positioning and Geomatics at the University of Rome “La Sapienza”. His investigation are in high-rate GNSS for seismology and ionospheric sounding; GNSS meteorological applications; ground and infrastructures deformations control and modeling; 3D objects and terrain modeling. He is co-inventor of two patents in the frame of GNSS positioning (VADASE, 2010) and high resolution optical and SAR satellite imagery processing (matching strategy, 2013).

Jan Kapłon, Prof, PhD, MSc, received a Ph.D. in Geodesy and Cartography in 2008 from Faculty of Environmental and Life Sciences of UPWr. His interest is focused on the retrieval of near real-time state of troposphere using GNSS as well as on satellite methods for high-rate determination of positions and deformation monitoring. He has been involved in 12 government funded scientific projects, e.g. EPOS-PL and EPOS-PL+ - European Plate observing System, near real-time model of the state of troposphere for the area of Poland from GNSS and meteorological data.

5.3.2 GNSS-seismology tutorials

Sessions/workload: 3 hours (23.09.2022, 9:00-10:30 & 11:00-12:30)

Teaching delivery methods: Practical interactive learning, also by the usage of a multimedia, work with a specialised software

Content overview: Students individually perform all stages of GNSS processing with RTKlib and time series analysis methods using an obspy numerical computing environment for chosen geodetic and geophysical time series, following the tutorial presented by the professor, i.e.: time series filtration and time-frequency analysis

Learning objectives: By the end of this course students will be able to use RTKlib and VADASE software for GNSS data processing at the basic level, to perform basic GNSS-signal processing with the use of PYTHON-obsPY software.

Lecturers: Jan Kapłon and

Augusto Mazzoni, Prof. PhD, MSc, received his PhD in Infrastructure and Transports, curriculum in Geomatics in 2009 at Sapienza University of Rome, Italy. He is Associate Professor within Geodesy and Geomatics Division at the Sapienza University of Rome. His recent investigation topics are: high-rate GNSS for seismology, navigation and ionospheric sounding; GNSS meteorological applications; GNSS raw measurements on Android (member of GNSS Raw Measurements Task Force). He is co-inventor of one patent, in the frame of GNSS positioning (VADASE, 2010).

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Michela Ravanelli, PhD, MSc, received her PhD degree from the Geodesy and Geomatics Division of Sapienza University of Rome. She was awarded the Sapienza University Excellent Student Award in 2017. She was granted with the "Young author award" from Italian Society for Photogrammetry and Topography in 2017. Her research topics include GNSS, GNSS seismology, ionosphere remote sensing, ionosphere seismology, coupling and interaction of various natural hazards and the ionosphere.

Roberta Ravanelli, PhD, MSc, received her PhD in Geomatics from Sapienza University of Rome in 2017 and she is currently Assistant Professor at the Geodesy and Geomatics Division of the Sapienza University of Rome. Her research activities include image and point cloud processing and Geo and Remote Sensing Big Data analysis. In 2014 and 2015 she was selected as software developer within the Google Summer of Code (GSoc) international program, respectively with OSGeo (Open Source Geospatial Foundation) and OpenCV (Open Source Computer Vision library) organizations.

5.3.3 Field measurements (GNSS)

Sessions/workload: 1.5 hours (22.09.2022, 14:00-15:30)

Teaching delivery methods: Practical interactive learning

Content overview: Hands-on experiments with specialized equipment for GNSS measurements of seismic simulations, collection of data for the GNSS-seismology tutorial.

Learning objectives: By the end of this course students will be familiar with the planning and performing of experimental kinematic high-rate GNSS measurements and collection of data for research purposes in the field of GNSS-seismology.

Lecturers: Jan Kaplon and Augusto Mazzoni

5.4 Workshop

Sessions/workload: 2 hours (22.09.2022, 16:00-19:00)

Teaching delivery methods: Workshop

Content overview: A scientific seminar including presentations on InSAR, LiDAR, GNSS and GNSS-seismology for monitoring of surface deformations and remote sensing for land cover/land use change mapping. The presentations are given by PhD students and experienced researchers from UPWr who participated in the GATHERS training program. In addition chosen students from the school are invited to present remote sensing and positioning techniques that expanded the workshop scope.

Learning objectives: By the end of the workshop the students will be familiar with more fields of application of the studied geodetic techniques during the school by real examples for implementation of these techniques.

Topics and presenters:

“High-rate GNSS: application to mining tremors”, Iwona Kudłacik (UPWr, Poland)

„Integration of GNSS and 5G for precise positioning”, Chiara Pileggi and Marianna Alghisi (Politecnico di Milano, Italy)

„Integration of GNSS and InSAR observations for monitoring deformation of mining areas”, Damian Tondaś (UPWr, Poland)

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„Combined DInSAR-PSI approach for deformation map estimation in the area of underground coal mining exploitation”, Natalia Wielgocka (UPWr, Poland)

„Remote Sensing approaches for land use/land cover change detection in coastal areas and oceanic islands: A Review”, Rafaela Tiengo (cE3c: Centre for Ecology, Evolution and Environmental Changes & Azorean biodiversity group, Portugal)

„Instance segmentation of individual grains from a terrestrial laser scanning point cloud of a river bed”, Agata Walicka (UPWr, Poland)

„UAV-based laser scanning for the applications in agriculture and deformation monitoring”, Ansgar Dreier (University of Bonn, Germany)

„Adjustment of ULS strips collected with Velodyne VLP-16 laser scanner”, Grzegorz Józków (UPWr, Poland)

5.5 Group work

Sessions/workload: 4 hours (between 19 and 23.09.2022)

Teaching delivery methods: Work in groups and presentations

Content overview: The students are grouped in teams and work on individual, for each group, scientific tasks. These tasks are directly linked to the schools topics – InSAR, LiDAR, GNSS-seismology. The results are presented at the end of the school and evaluated by the leading lecturers for each topic.

Learning objectives: By the end of the task the students will develop more skills in team work, critical thinking, presenting. They will demonstrate understanding of InSAR, LIDAR & GNSS-seismology for deformation monitoring, discuss the potential advantages and disadvantages of each method.

5.6 Soft skills training

Sessions/workload: 3 hours (21.09.2022, 11:00-12:30 & 14:00-15:30)

Teaching delivery methods: Workshop

Content overview: “Explore your talents” - The training includes bringing out participant’s strengths, helping them to overcome internal barriers and limitations in order to function more effectively in a team. The main idea is to get out of their comfort zone following the motto “You can only grow if you are willing to feel weird and uncomfortable trying something completely new for you.”. The training also gives stress managements tips and plan.

Learning objectives: By the end of this course students will be able to understand their strengths and weaknesses in functioning in a team.

Lecturer: Sylwia Gašiorowska, has a long experience in coaching, career consulting. She cooperates with large corporations and different HR departments in team and business coaching, as well as in professional and life coaching.

5.7 Social skills development

Sessions/workload: 8 hours (between 19 and 23.09.2022)

Teaching delivery methods: Social and cultural communication

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Content overview: The participants of the school is given opportunity for social contact during welcome event and gala dinner. This gives opportunity for networking between participants from different universities, institutions, and also from different countries. In addition the cultural program includes guided tour in the hosting town of Wroclaw and a visit to the Museum of the Historical Mine Ignacy in Rybnik, Silesia, Poland.

Learning objectives: By the end of the school the students will be part of the GATHERS scientific network by developing stronger social skills, and also creating social and cultural links within the group of the school, including lecturers.

6 Courses program

	Monday 19 September 2022	Tuesday 20 September 2022	Wednesday 21 September 2022	Thursday 22 September 2022	Friday 23 September 2022	Saturday 24 September 2022
	Wroclaw	Wroclaw	Wroclaw / Rybnik	Rybnik	Rybnik	Rybnik / Wroclaw
09:00-10:30	09:00 - 09:30 Registration (building C2) Opening session (room II G)	InSAR tutorial (room 102 G)	LiDAR tutorial (room 102 G)	GNSS theory	GNSS tutorial	Travel to Wroclaw (departire at 8:30)
10:30-11:00	Photo & coffee break	Coffee break	Coffee break	Coffee break	Coffee break	
11:00-12:30	InSAR theory (room II G)	LiDAR theory (room II G)	Soft skills trainings (room 202 G)	GNSS theory	GNSS tutorial	
12:30-14:00	LUNCH	LUNCH	LUNCH	LUNCH	LUNCH	
14:00-15:30	InSAR theory (room II G)	LiDAR theory (room II G)	Soft skills trainings (room 202 G)	Field measurements (GNSS)	Field measurements (UAV)	
15:30-16:00	Coffee break	Coffee break		Coffee break	Coffee break	
16:00-18:00	InSAR tutorial (room 102 G)	LiDAR tutorial (room 102 G)	Travel to Rybnik (departure at 15:45)	Workshop	Museum visit	
18:30-20:30	Welcome event (building A2)	City guided tour (departure at 18:15)		Gala dinner	School results and diploma ceremony	

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